

Job Stress and Organizational Commitment of Deposit Money Bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State

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Abstract

The study evaluated the Job stress and organizational commitment of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between long hours work and employee communication skills; and evaluate the relationship between heavy workload and employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State. The study adopted descriptive survey. The primary source of data was questionnaire. The total population for the study was one thousand, one hundred and twenty three (1123). The adequate sample size of 286, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 265 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was analyzed and the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to test the hypotheses. Findings showed that Long hours work had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State, $r(95, n = 265), = .420 < .733, p < .05$). Heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State, $r(95, n = 265), = .570 < .737, p < .05$). The study concluded that long hours work and Heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills and employee relation of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that for effective long hours work there is need for a more flexible workforce. This will enhance the ability to deal with bottlenecks, busy periods, and cover of absences and staff shortages without the need to recruit extra staff and increased earning for employees and mutual employer benefit.

Keywords *Job Stress; Organizational Commitment; Deposit Money Bank; Rivers State*

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Introduction

Today, the deposit money banks (DBM) have been experiencing constant changes in their business operations. The organizations have increased in its competitiveness as result of the new coming of other financing banks and the increasing need of customers. These situations require a deposit money banks (DBM) to provide good quality services and it is expected to do better in providing the various demands of the customers which are constantly changing in daily basis by giving them fast, appropriate, and reliable services. For this to be successful, deposit money banks (DBM) depend on the inputs of the staff that are often known as the lifeblood of every institution. Therefore, for the bank operations to be conducted effectively, it is very essential for the banks to perform at their very best to achieve the institution's goals or objectives. Therefore, it is very important for the banks to make serious effort to diversify some many strategies or methods to keep their staff comfortable and stress free. But in nowadays work life, staff are generally required to work extensively for longer hours to meet their expectations about work performance as the need on them increases on everyday activities and this exerts high increase of stress on them (Fonkeng, 2019).

It has been discovered very often that studies of so-called healthy firms or industry points that policies benefiting worker health also benefit the bottom line. A healthy firms or industry is defined as one that has reduced rates of sickness, injury, and disability in its staff workforce and competitive in the marketplace. The national institute for occupational safety and health (NIOSH) research has observed the organizational characteristics associated with both healthy, low-stress work and high levels of output. Some of these characteristics include: Recognition of workers or staff for quality work performance, chances for career development, workplace culture that values the individual worker and Management actions that they are reliable with organizational values (The national institute for occupational safety and health (NIOSH, 2023).

Stress in organization has affected almost very professions, beginning from the top-level executives, to other workers who are mainly involved in the area of the job. The outcome of the job stress seriously affects the physical plus mental health. Job stress is a condition in which any human is confronted with an opportunity or demand related to what they desire and for which the outcome is perceived to be both uncertain and important (Daniel,2019). Work stress is the reaction people will have when presented with work needs and pressures that are not related to their experiences and abilities and which opposes their ability to meet up with. Stress appears in a wide range of work situations but sometimes made worse when workers feel they have less support from managers and colleagues and where they have less control over the job or how they can cope or meet up with its needs and pressures (Saranya & Sudhaha, 2016)

Organizational commitment plays a vital role especially in the banking industry in determining how a worker will work with the organization for a longer period of time and work passionately towards achieving the organization's goal. An employee's level of stress depends on the organizational commitment towards his/her work. Employee satisfaction, employee engagement, distribution of leadership, job performance toward, job insecurity, and similar such attributes affects employee job stress positively if managed well. In the recent business perspectives, a turn in efficiency model based on organizational commitment is needed. Business firms need to form groups or teams that are seriously committed to their strategic goals, meant toward industry and work (Herrera and Heras-Rosas, 2021; Mbah, Nwatu & Okwor, 2021). Based on this, the need to study Job stress and organizational of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The dynamic nature of work is on high speed and is increasing on the recent job performance. Perhaps now more than ever before, job stress poses a threat to the health of workers and, in turn, to the health organizations. Everyone reacts in much the same situations, irrespective of whether the stressful situation is at work or home. Stresses are as a result of poor interpersonal relationship at work environment, when workers find unsupportive environment or any personal notice from others at work place.

Job stress affect employee performance when stress is not handled well, poor employee communication skills, poor employee relation, absenteeism, turnover and medical compensation increase and output decreases. To actualize a peak of success, stress should be managed effectively, with the negative effects of stress minimized.

The employees may think of leaving their job and felt that the organization did not care about them, this will show a reflection of huge dissatisfaction that undoubtedly will lower performance. The organization must conduct a needs assessment for an Employee help Programme for early identification and intervention on challenges so that performance levels will improve. This has necessitated the need to study Job stress and organizational of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective was to evaluate the Job stress and organizational commitment of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between long hours work and employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between heavy workload and employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State.

Research Questions

The following Research Questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between long hours work and employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State?
- ii. What is the relationship between heavy workload and employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study

- i. Long hours work has relationship with the employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State.
- ii. Heavy workload has relationship with the employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State.

Significance of the Study

The debilitating working conditions of the workers.

Organizations: The study serves as an important tool to analyse and evaluate job stress and organizational commitment in deposit money banks in Nigeria. It will also help various organizations on how to structure their organization job stress for easy adaptation.

The study will also help managers to know the importance of job stress and also the use of incentives to reduce stress in the organizations. It also serves as a point of reference to all stakeholders in the deposit money banks on the need to provide healthy work environment to increase employee performance and productivity.

Researcher: The study serves as reference material for the researcher and students who intend to carry out studies on the related topic of the study.

Scope of the Study

The focus of the study is on Job stress and organizational commitment of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State. The study variables were long hours work and Heavy workload; (independent variables) while employee communication skills and employee relation in Deposit money bank (dependent variables) of the study.

Conceptual Review

Job Stress

Job stress is the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker. Job stress matters to our health and our work. When we feel stressed, our bodies respond by raising the concentration of stress hormones in our blood. When our bodies continually respond to constant demands or threats, coping mechanisms stay in overdrive, which can be damaging to health over time. Research shows that excessive job stress can lead to many long-term health problems, including cardiovascular disease, diabetes, weakened immune function, high blood pressure, musculoskeletal disorders, substance abuse, depression and anxiety (Umass, 2023). Stress is not always bad. A little bit of stress can help you stay focused, energetic, and able to meet new challenges in the workplace. It is what keeps you on your toes during a presentation or alert to prevent accidents or costly mistakes. But in today's hectic world, the workplace too often seems like an emotional roller coaster. Long hours, tight deadlines, and ever-increasing demands can leave you feeling worried, drained, and overwhelmed. And when stress exceeds your ability to cope, it stops being helpful and starts causing damage to your mind and body as well as to your job satisfaction (Segal, Melinda and Robinson, 2023).

Components of Job Stress used in the Study

Long Hours Work

Overtime is working more hours than your contract requires. In some cases, working overtime may be voluntary, but it may be mandatory in other cases. Sometimes there are financial incentives to work overtime, such as time and half wages and bonuses. Working overtime has long been seen as a badge of honor in the business world. If you're working late, you must be working hard! However, recent research has shown that working overtime may not be as good for business as we thought. In some cases, there is no reward for working overtime. It is expected and demanded of employees and is woven into their contract. The most extreme example of this is "crunch time," which is common in the game industry. Companies require their staff to work extra hours and days to ensure the game releases on time (Tom, 2023). While remote work has given us the freedom to create our own schedule and skip the stressful commute, it's not all it's cracked up to be. With more pressure to keep up with various communication channels, working long hours is occasionally part of the deal. Even if it might mean earning more, constantly putting in too many hours is a surefire way to burn out if you're not careful. The average working hours vary across countries but researchers from the Australian National University are advocating for a limit of no more than 39 hours a week. Working more than that could put your mental and physical health at risk and it's not hard to see why (Rebollido, 2023).

Heavy Workload

A heavy workload is when the amount of responsibilities one has pushes the boundaries of what can realistically be done in a given role. It can be the result of a business trying to trim costs, but it can also come from how work is delegated to or managed by the individual. Acknowledging a heavy workload is an important first step toward seeking balance and reaching your career goals. The determining factors of when a workload becomes too heavy are subjective, but if the quality of your work is suffering or your personal life or health are being adversely affected by your job, your workload may be too heavy (Herrity, 2022). A heavy workload is a workload that requires you to use your time management skills to juggle multiple tasks, responsibilities, and projects in order to successfully complete them on time without sacrificing the quality of your work. This is a type of behavioral interview question. These types of questions ask you to describe your past actions or predict how you'll react in future situations. These can be great ways to get insight into your personality and how you approach difficult situations (Mckee and Arcand, 2022).

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is defined as a view of an organization's member's psychology towards his/her attachment to the organization that he/she is working for. Organizational commitment plays a pivotal role in determining whether an employee will stay with the organization for a longer period of time and work passionately towards achieving the organization's goal. If an organizational commitment is determined it helps predict employee satisfaction, employee engagement, distribution of leadership, job performance, job insecurity, and similar such

attributes (Questionpro, 2023). Organizational commitment refers to the level of engagement and dedication team members feel toward their individual jobs and the organization. It also describes the different reasons professionals remain with an employer rather than seek opportunities elsewhere. Affective commitment refers to the psychological connection that an individual has with an organization. It describes team members who want to further their involvement with their company and play an active role in its development because they enjoy their work (IndeedTutorialTeam, 2023).

Components of Organizational Commitment used in the Study

Employee Communication Skills

Communication skills are abilities you use when giving and receiving different kinds of information. While these skills may be a regular part of your day-to-day work life, communicating in a clear, effective and efficient way is an extremely critical and useful skill. Employers consistently included communication skills as one of the most commonly requested skills in job postings. Improving and showcasing your communication skills can help you advance in your career and stay competitive in today's job market (Northup, 2023). Employee communication is often defined as the sharing of information and ideas between the management of an organization and employees and vice versa. It is essential for an organization's success that there are many different channels available to communicate with your employees as well as your customers. Social media definitely has certainly increased the scope of communication (Questionpro, 2023). Workplace communication is the exchange of information between employees in a work environment. This includes face-to-face conversations, emails, chat messages, videoconferencing, phone calls, and other methods used to convey information in the workplace. Nonverbal communication like eye contact, body language, and tone of voice are also important aspects of workplace communication (Coursera, 2023; Mbah, Ede, & Ugochukwu, 2018).

Employee Relation

Employee relations refer to the relationship between or among an employer and its employees. Depending on the context, the term has both practical and theoretical applications. Certain companies may have a dedicated team for maintaining and improving employee relations and this term may refer to this team. In other cases, the term may refer to theories, plans and policies designed to support employees and their interests. Regardless of the approach, employee relations are typically overseen by a company's human resources department. Employee relations concerns the building of positive relationships and interactions among employers and employees, and at a broader level helps foster a sense of community within an organization (Crail, 2023). The definition of employee relations refers to an organization's efforts to create and maintain a positive relationship with its employees. By maintaining positive, constructive employee relations, organizations hope to keep employees loyal and more engaged in their work. Typically, an organization's human resources department manages employee relations efforts; however, some organizations may have a dedicated employee relations manager role. To maintain positive employee relations, an organization must first view employees as stakeholders and contributors in the company rather than simply as paid laborers (Bamboohr, 2023).

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Theoretical Framework

Systemic Stress: Hans Selye (1907–1982) guided the work

The popularity of the stress concept stems largely comes from the work of the endocrinologist Hans Selye. He defines stress as 'a state manifested by a syndrome which consists of all the nonspecifically induced changes in a biologic system.' This stereotypical response pattern, called the 'General Adaptation Syndrome' (GAS), proceeds in three stages. (a) The alarm reaction comprises an initial shock phase and a subsequent counter shock phase. The shock phase exhibits autonomic excitability, an increased adrenaline discharge, and gastrointestinal ulcerations. The counter shock phase marks the initial operation of defensive processes and is characterized by increased adrenocortical activity. (b) If noxious stimulation continues, the organism enters the stage of resistance. In this stage, the symptoms of the alarm reaction disappear, which seemingly indicates the organism's adaptation to the stressors. However, while resistance to the noxious stimulation increases, resistance to other kinds of stressors decreases at the same time. (c) If the aversive stimulation persists, resistance gives way to the stage of exhaustion. The organism's capability of adapting to the stressors is exhausted, the symptoms of stage (a) reappear, but resistance is no longer possible. Irreversible tissue damages appear, and, if the stimulation persists, the organism dies. Although Selye, fails to take into account coping mechanisms as important mediators of the stress–outcome relationship, his theory serves to explain the detriments of stress of interventions are not made in time to rescue the stressed individuals. This theory indirectly underpins the importance of stress management strategies to avoid employees reaching the irreversible stage when the stress is more advanced. With adequate intervention measures that are applied in time, employees' commitment may be restored and therefore their productivity.

Empirical Review

The Relationship between Long Hour's Work and Employee Communication Skills of Deposit Money Bank in PortHarcourt, Rivers State.

Tamunomiebi (2018) conducted a study on Quality of Work Life and Employee Job Satisfaction in Deposit Money Banks in PortHarcourt, Rivers State. This study focused on the relationship between quality of work life and employee job satisfaction in deposit money banks in PortHarcourt. The study adopted a cross sectional research design and used questionnaire as the primary source of data collection. A sample of one hundred and eighty-eight (188) respondents were drawn from a population of three hundred and fifty five (355) respondents across the seven selected Money Deposit Banks in PortHarcourt, Nigeria using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. After data cleaning, only data of 151 respondents were finally used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics and Spearman's rank correlation were used for data analysis and hypothesis testing. Results revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between quality of work life and employee job satisfaction. The study thus concludes that quality of work life bears a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction in deposit money banks in PortHarcourt.

Nweke (2020) conducted a study on Office Communication and Staff Performance in Money Deposit Banks in PortHarcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The main objective of this study was to look at Office Communication and Staff Performance in Money Deposit Banks in PortHarcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The study was based on empirical study of communication and office performance. It studied a population size 100 staff each of the five branches of Ecobank, Rumuola Road, GT Bank, Location Junction, UBA, Rumuokwuta, Fidelity Rumuokwuta, First Bank Plc Rumuola branches. A sample size of 20 representing 5% of the total population was studied adopting the purposive sampling technique. Three research questions and three null hypotheses were raised. The hypotheses were tested using Chi-square statistical tool. The research findings showed, Ho1, that there is a significant relationship between business office staff knowledge of modern communications skills and their performance. Ho2 there is a there is significant relationship between business office staff use of communication skills and their performance in financial institutions in PortHarcourt Metropolis. Ho3, there is no significant between non-availability of communication tools and performance of business office staff in financial institutions in PortHarcourt Metropolis. The on the findings the study recommended; that management should encourage their staff to be knowledgeable in modern communication skills since it has significant relationship with performance of their staff. Training of staff can be such encouragements in the various business offices of the banks.

Mekuri-Ndimele (2020) conducted a study on Work flexibility and employee performance in deposit money banks in PortHarcourt. The study examined the relationship between work flexibility and employee performance in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study adopted a cross sectional survey research design that solicited responses from employees of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. Primary data was collated using structured questionnaire. The population of the study comprised 202 employees of 18 Deposit Money Banks operational in Rivers State. A sample size of 134 was determined using the Taro Yamen sample size formula. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 23.0. The study findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between work flexibility and employee performance in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study concluded that work flexibility bears a significant influence on employee performance in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State.

Ogbonda (2023) conducted a study on Work Environment and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. This study examined the relationship work environment and organizational performance of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey in its investigation of the variables. Primary data was generated through structured, self- administered questionnaire. The population of the study is 72 managers (4 managers from each) of the 18 Deposit Money Banks operating in Rivers State. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient. The tests were carried out at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between work environment and organizational performance of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. Therefore, the study concludes that creating a conducive work environment positively enhance performance of deposit money banks in Rivers State.

Uranta and Kemi (2023) conducted a study on Motivation and Employee Heterogeneity of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. This study examined the relationship between motivation and employee heterogeneity of deposit money banks in Rivers State. Cross sectional research design was adopted in studying the deposit money banks in Olu Obasanjo Road, PortHarcourt. Two-hundred and thirty-two (232) copies of questionnaire were retrieved and analyzed from the field survey out of two-hundred and fifty- nine (259) distributed. Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient statistical tool was employed to ascertain the relationship existing between the variables. Findings revealed a positive non-significant relationship between the predictor variable (motivation) and the measures of employee heterogeneity (gender and age heterogeneity). It was concluded that motivation non-significantly relates positively to employee heterogeneity of deposit money banks in Rivers State. The study suggested that CBN increase its routine bank inspections to make sure that the banks are following industry best practices. Deposit money bank management should make sure that employees are adequately motivated in line with industry best practices.

The Relationship between Heavy Workload and Employee Relation of Deposit Money Bank in Portharcourt, River State.

Kenneth, and Omunakwe (2018) conducted a study on Workplace Interpersonal Relationship and Organizational Growth in Deposit Money Banks in PortHarcourt. The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between Workplace Interpersonal Relationship and Organizational Growth in deposit money banks in PortHarcourt. The study population comprised four hundred and sixty (460) staff of the (19) quoted money deposit banks in PortHarcourt, Rivers State; and the sample size for the study was two hundred and ten (210) employees of the bank which was determined using the Krejice and Morgan (1970) table. Furthermore, two hundred and ten (210) copies of structured questionnaire were administered to the staff of the banks at their respective branches while one hundred and ninety four (194) were retrieved, cleaned and used for the study. The multiple linear regressions were used to ascertain the dimension of Workplace Interpersonal Relationship with the most predictive influence on Organizational Growth. The result of the analysis revealed that Workplace Interpersonal Relationship significantly influenced organizational growth in deposit money banks in PortHarcourt. The study further revealed that amongst the dimensions of Workplace Interpersonal Relationship used in this study that Social Support and Relational Justice were found to be the most significant predictors of Organizational Growth in money deposit banks in PortHarcourt. Hence, the researchers concluded that Workplace Interpersonal Relationship significantly affect organizational growth.

Ewwierhoma and Oga (2020) conducted a study on Enhancing Employee's Commitment of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State through Affinitive Managerial Humor Practices. The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship

between Affinitive humor practices and employee commitment (affective, continuance and normative commitment) of deposit money banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. A survey design was adopted for the study using questionnaire as the research instrument which was distributed to 285 employees working in the banks. The generated data were analyzed through the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient in order to test the relationship between the variables of the study through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Windows version 22 within a significance level of 0.05. The findings showed that Affinitive humor practices has significant influence on employee commitment vis-a-vis affective, continuance and normative commitment respectively.

Bestman and Okparaji (2021) conducted a study on Big Data Management and Employee Resilience of Deposit Money Banks in PortHarcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between Big Data Management and Employee Resilience of Deposit Money Banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Primary data was generated through self- administered questionnaire. This study was conducted in 17 Deposit Money Banks in PortHarcourt, Rivers State. The study used descriptive technique through the adoption of cross sectional research survey design. A total population of one hundred and two (102) managerial staff of the target banks was studied. A census sampling was adopted since the population was small. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0. The results of analysed data showed the dimensions of big data management (data volume and data variety) significantly correlated positively with the measures of employee resilience; adaptive capacity and situational awareness. The study concludes that big data management significantly predicted employee resilience in Deposit Money Banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Agwuma (2022) conducted a study on Non-Statutory Welfare System and Employee Productivity of Deposit Money Banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. This study empirically examined the relationship between non-statutory welfare system and employee productivity of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The study adopted the cross-sectional survey design in its methodology. The population of the study was 200 employees of the selected banks while its sample size was 133 as determined using Taro Yaman formula. The Cronbach Alpha value scale threshold of 0.7 was exceeded which indicated the reliability of the scales used in the study. Statistical analysis was carried out at two levels; descriptive statistics and charts were done at the primary level while Spearman Ranked Ordered Correlation was used at the secondary level with the aid of Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0. Given the findings drawn from the analysis, it was concluded that the application of non-statutory welfare system in the management of organization's workforce within the context of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt is a critical recipe for sustained employee productivity.

Oloboh (2022) conducted a study on Employee Competence and Work Engagement of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. This study examined the relationship between employee competence and work engagement of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study utilized a cross-sectional survey design. Primary data were sourced through structured and self- administered questionnaire. The population of the study comprised 283 staff of twenty-two (22) deposit money banks in Port Harcourt; whereas a sample size of one hundred and sixty-five (165) staff was drawn through the Taro Yamane formulae. The reliability of the instrument was determined by the use of the Cronbach Alpha Ccoefficient, with 0.70 as benchmark. Data generated were presented with tables and descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Statistics. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between competence and work engagement of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study concludes that when employees are empowered through competence improvement, work engagement is enhanced.

Gap in Empirical Review

The few studies done were carried outside Job stress and organizational commitment of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the long hours work and employee communication skills; and heavy workload and employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present

study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the Job stress and organizational commitment of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State.

Methodology

The target population of the study consist of 21 registered deposit money banks in Portharcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria from which eight (8) banks were selected that have international authorization. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. The total population for the study was one thousand, one hundred and twenty three (1123). The adequate sample size of 286, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 265 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 93 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.78 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

Relationship between Long Hours Work and Employee Communication Skills and Deposit Money Bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State.

Table 1: Responses to research question one on the relationship between long hours work and employee communication skills and deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision	
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X			
1	The long hours of work is sustained with Effective collaboration of the employee.	525 105 39.6	316 79 29.8	42 16 6.0	58 29 10.9	36 36 13.6	977 265 100%		3.71	1.428	Agree
2	The length of hours in the bank is promoted by the team work which boosts employee morale.	440 88 33.2	316 79 29.8	75 25 9.4	36 18 6.8	55 55 20.8	922 265 100%		3.48	1.518	Agree
3	Effective communication helps drive better results for the organization during so many hours of use.	450 90 34.0	372 93 35.1	78 26 9.8	40 20 7.5	36 36 13.6	976 265 100%		3.68	1.367	Agree
4	The consecutiveness at work reduces stress and employee fell in their best.	505 101 38.1	340 85 32.1	21 7 2.6	84 42 15.8	30 30 11.3	980 265 100%		3.70	1.406	Agree
5	Long hours work is built by effective communication at work which boosts employee morale.	490 98 37.0	340 85 32.1	54 18 6.8	40 20 7.5	44 44 16.6	968 265 100%		3.65	1.457	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation									3.644	1.4352	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 184 respondents out of 265 representing 69.4 percent agreed that the long hours of work is sustained with Effective collaboration of the employee with mean score 3.71 and a standard deviation of 1.428. The length of hours in the bank is promoted by the team work which boosts employee morale 167 respondents representing 63.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.518. Effective communication helps drive better results for the organization during so many hours of use 183 respondents representing 69.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.68 and standard deviation of 1.367. The consecutiveness at work reduces stress and employee fell in their best 186 respondents representing 70.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.70 and 1.406. Long hours work is built by effective communication at work which boosts employee morale 183. respondents representing 69.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.65 and a standard deviation of 1.457.

The Relationship between Heavy Workload and Employee Relation of Deposit Money Bank in Portharcourt, River State

Table 2: Responses to research question two on the relationship between heavy workload and employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Workload shows a strong relation with turnover of employee.	480 96 36. 2	428 107 40. 4	21 7 2.6	86 43 16. 2	12 12 4.5	1.27 265 100%	3.88	1.198	Agree
2	High workload exceeding one's ability more as work stress	395 79 29. 8	428 107 40. 4	3 1 4	76 38 14. 3	40 40 15.1	942 265 100%	3.55	1.429	Agree
3	Heavy work load lead to cost of skilled employee	435 87 32. 8	436 109 41. 1	18 6 2.3	72 36 13. 6	27 27 10.2	988 265 100%	3.73	1.321	Agree
4	Increase in expenditure of high education expense for new employee occurs because of workload	480 96 36. 2	356 89 33. 6	69 23 8.7	12 6 2.3	51 51 19.3	968 265 100%	3.65	1.469	Agree
5	Job insecurity and conflicts with co-worker or bosses are experienced with workload.	545 109 41. 1	396 74 27. 9	42 14 5.3	84 42 15. 8	26 26 9.8	1066 265 100%	3.75	1.387	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.712	1.3608	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 203 respondents out of 265 representing 76.6 percent agreed that the Workload shows a strong relation with turnover of employee with mean score 3.88 and a standard deviation of 1.198. High workload exceeding one's ability more as work stress 186 respondents representing 70.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.55 and a standard deviation of 1.429. Heavy work load lead to cost of skilled employee 196 respondents representing 73.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.73 and standard deviation of 1.321. Increase in expenditure of high education expense for new employee occurs because of workload 185 respondents representing 69.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.65 and 1.469. Job insecurity and conflicts with co-worker or bosses are experienced with workload 183 respondents representing 69.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.75 and a standard deviation of 1.387

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Long Hours Work has Relationship with the Employee Communication Skills of Deposit Money Bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State.

Table 3

		Correlations				
		The long hours of work is sustained with effective collaboration of the employees.	The length of hours in the bank is promoted by the team work which boosts employee morale.	Effective communication helps drive better results for the organization during so many hours of use.	The consecutiveness at work reduces stress and employee feel in their best.	Long hours work is built by effective communication at work which boosts employee morale.
The long hours of work is sustained with effective collaboration of the employees.	Pearson Correlation	1	.735**	.731**	.630**	.656**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
The length of hours in the bank is promoted by the team work which boosts employee morale.	Pearson Correlation	.735**	1	.654**	.569**	.523**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
Effective communication helps drive better results for the organization during so many hours of use.	Pearson Correlation	.731**	.654**	1	.620**	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
The consecutiveness at work reduces stress and employee feel in their best.	Pearson Correlation	.630**	.569**	.620**	1	.689**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
Long hours work is built by effective communication at work which boosts employee morale.	Pearson Correlation	.656**	.523**	.764**	.689**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	265	265	265	265	265

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on long hours work and employee communication skills showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.420 < .733$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that long hours work had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State. ($r = .420 < .733$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .420 < .733, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .420 < .733$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that long hours work had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .420 < .733, p < .05$).

Hypothesis Two: Heavy Workload has Relationship with the Employee Relation of Deposit Money Bank in Portharcourt, River State.

Table 4: Correlations

		Workload shows a strong relation with turnover of employees.	High workload exceeding one's ability more as work stress.	Heavy work load lead to cost of skilled employees	Increase in expenditure of high education expanse for new employee occurs because of workload.	Job insecurity and conflicts with co-worker or bosses are experienced with workload.
Workload shows a strong relation with turnover of employees.	Pearson Correlation	1	.735**	.737**	.649**	.626**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
High workload exceeding one's ability more as work stress.	Pearson Correlation	.735**	1	.726**	.633**	.648**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
Heavy work load lead to cost of skilled employees	Pearson Correlation	.737**	.726**	1	.634**	.616**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
Increase in expenditure of high education expanse for new employee occurs because of workload.	Pearson Correlation	.649**	.633**	.634**	1	.570**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	265	265	265	265	265
Job insecurity and conflicts with co-worker or bosses are experienced with workload.	Pearson Correlation	.626**	.648**	.616**	.570**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	265	265	265	265	265

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on heavy workload and employee relation showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.570 < .737$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee relation of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State ($r = .570 < .737$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .570 < .737, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .570 < .737$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .570 < .737, p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

The Relationship between Long Hours Work and Employee Communication Skills

From the result of hypothesis one, the computed ($r = .420 < .733$) was greater than the table value of $.000$, we concluded that long hours work had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .420 < .733, p < .05$). In the support of the result in the literature review, Mekuri-Ndimele (2020). Conducted a study on Work flexibility and employee performance in deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. The study findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between work flexibility and employee performance in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State.

The study concluded that work flexibility bears a significant influence on employee performance in Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. Ogbonda (2023), conducted a study on Work Environment and Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. This study examined the relationship work environment and organizational performance of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between work environment and organizational performance of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State.

The Relationship between Heavy Workload and Employee Relation

From the result of hypothesis two, the computed ($r = .570 < .737$) was greater than the table value of .000, we concluded that heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, River State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .570 < .737, p < .05$). In the support of the result in the literature review, Ewrierhoma, and Oga (2020) conducted a study on Enhancing Employee's Commitment of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State through Affinitive Managerial Humor Practices. The findings showed that Affinitive humor practices have significant influence on employee commitment vis-a-vis affective, continuance and normative commitment respectively. Bestman, and Okparaji (2021) conducted a study on Big Data Management and Employee Resilience of Deposit Money Banks in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The results of analyzed data showed the dimensions of big data management (data volume and data variety) significantly correlated positively with the measures of employee resilience; adaptive capacity and situational awareness. Oloboh (2022), conducted a study on Employee Competence and Work Engagement of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between competence and work engagement of Deposit Money Banks in Rivers State. The study concludes that when employees are empowered through competence improvement, work engagement is enhanced.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results, the following findings were made:

- i. Long hours work had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State, $r (95, n = 265) = .420 < .733, p < .05$
- ii. Heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee relation of Deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State, $r (95, n = 265) = .570 < .737, p < .05$.

Conclusion

The study concluded that long hours work and Heavy workload had significant positive relationship with the employee communication skills and employee relation of deposit money bank in Portharcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Stress is not always bad. A little bit of stress can help you stay focused, energetic, and able to meet new challenges in the workplace. It is what keeps you on your toes during a presentation or alert to prevent accidents or costly mistakes. Therefore, it is very important for the banks to make serious effort to diversify some many strategies or methods to keep their staff comfortable and stress free. But in nowadays work life, staff is generally required to work extensively for longer hours to meet their expectations about work performance as the need arises.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following the recommendations were proffered

- i. For effective long hours work there is need for a more flexible workforce. This will enhance the ability to deal with bottlenecks, busy periods, and cover of absences and staff shortages without the need to recruit extra staff and increased earning for employees and mutual employer benefit.
- ii. The bank management should be able to manage a heavy workload to impress employers and increase the value in the organization. Managing a heavy workload can get a lot done without relying on others.

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